

Magnetic susceptibilities of pulses, grams, grains and seeds

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The effect of powdering on the magnetic susceptibility of many common pulses, grains and seeds of India was studied. A systematic magnetic behavioural change occurred in the samples upon mechanical crushing. The ESR spectrum and the chemical composition of the substances reveal the presence of paramagnetic centres under mechanical stress. Wheat barn showed distinct paramagnetic behavior. Green gram husk, black gram husk and red gram husk showed definite paramagnetism while the corresponding dhal showed diamagnetism. The oils were diamagnetic but their corresponding cakes showed a net paramagnetism. The concentration of free radicals formed during powdering or crushing increased with increasing fineness of the sample. The ESR signal produced in this work showed remarkable stability even after one month of crushing and at different storage conditions. Irradiation of the samples by UV, X-rays and γ -rays did not cause any change in the magnetic susceptibility of the samples.

A systematic analysis was undertaken to study the effect of powdering on the magnetic susceptibility of many common pulses, grains, grams and seeds of India. As reported earlier¹ a paramagnetic behavior crept into the specimen by the process of mechanical crushing or powdering though originally being diamagnetic.

The specimen studied were : green gram (*Vigna radiata*), black gram (*Vigna mungo*), red gram (*Cajanus cajan*), bengal gram (*Cicer arietinum*), horse gram (*Dolichos biflorus*), cow pea (*Vigna unguiculata*), peas (*Pisum sativum*), millet (*Perisetum typhoides*), ragi (*Eleusine coracana*), wheat (*Triticum aestivum*), paddy and rice (*Oryza sativa*), fenugreek (*Trigonella foenum – graecum*), cumin seeds (*Cuminum cynium*), carun copticum or carum ajowan (*Trachyspermum ammi*), black pepper (*Piper nigrum*), coriander seeds (*Coriandrum sativum*), turmeric (*Curcuma longa*), chilli (*Capsicum annuum*). The seed and the dhal without husk were studied. Finally, the whole seed was crushed, and the magnetic susceptibilities of the powder at different levels of crushing were measured. The ESR spectrum of each specimen was taken to confirm the paramagnetic character of the specimen after crushing.

The method of processing the analytes, measurement of magnetic properties and analysis of data were same as described earlier¹.

Results and Discussion

The results presented here show a systematic magnetic behavioural change in the samples upon mechanical crush-

ing. The ESR spectrum and the chemical compositions of the substances reveal the presence of paramagnetic centres under mechanical stress.

The green gram seed and the dhal without husk have the same value of diamagnetic susceptibility (Table 1). However, when the whole seed was crushed and the magnetic susceptibility of the powder at different levels of crushing was measured, there was a change in the diamagnetic susceptibility. The dhal did not show any appreciable change in magnetic character on crushing. In the seed, a decrease in diamagnetic susceptibility indicated some paramagnetic contributions from the constituents upon crushing. This contribution might have come from the husk of the seeds as is evident from the foregoing results. The husk showed a definite paramagnetism (Table 1). The fibrous outer cover of the seeds seems to have experienced some complex formation upon grinding as compared to the de-husked dhal. Moreover, the B-vitamins, some of the constituents of the material are concentrated in the cells adjacent to the cotyledons and there is every chance of these forming a metal complex with the traces of minerals available in the husk; another possibility, as pointed out by Assenheim², free radicals may have formed by the breakage of the molecular chains.

The ESR signal shows a g value of 2.006 at room temperature. This could be compared with the g value 2.003 ± 0.003 of potassium aluminium selenium oxide complex $[KAl(SeO_4).12H_2O]$ $g = 2.005$ of $MnSiF_6.6H_2O$ with the ratio Mn : Mg (or Mn : Zn = 1 : 20–1 : 150 and Mn : Zn =

10^{-3} or rubidium aluminium sulfate $[\text{RbAl}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ of g value of 2.003 ± 0.003 . Since Mn, Si, Rb and Al are present as trace elements it is likely that the complex might be due to potassium, which is available in comparatively larger quantities.

Table 1. Volume magnetic susceptibility (in 10^{-6} cgs units) of pulses, grams, grains and seeds

Substance	Fineness (Average thickness of the sample)			
	Seed	0.5 mm	0.2 mm	0.1 mm
	Green gram	-0.531	-0.482	-0.371
Green gram dhal (dehusked)	-0.530	-0.522	-0.521	-0.510
Green gram husk				+3.121
Black gram	-0.550	-0.473	-0.282	-0.112
Black gram dhal (dehusked)	-0.548	-0.540	-0.500	-0.499
Black gram husk				+5.197
Red gram	-0.562	-0.492	-0.265	-0.217
Red gram dhal (dehusked)	-0.556	-0.509	-0.500	-0.499
Red gram husk				+1.925
Bengal gram	-0.482	-0.382	+0.112	+0.158
Bengal gram dhal (dehusked)	-0.481	-0.381	+0.100	+0.109
Bengal gram husk				-0.072
Horse gram	-0.501	-0.452	-0.305	-0.299
Cowpea (ordinary)	-0.482	-0.455	-0.320	-0.300
Cowpea (white variety)	-0.411	-0.400	-0.311	-0.300
Cowpea (red variety)	-0.401	-0.311	-0.288	-0.255
Cowpea (red big variety)	-0.400	-0.302	-0.292	-0.212
Peas (green)	-0.481	-0.402	-0.231	-0.084
Peas (dried and roasted)	-0.411	-0.381	-0.211	-0.077
Millet (first quality)	-0.595	-0.465	-0.242	-0.221
Millet (second quality)	-0.562	-0.441	-0.253	-0.201
Maize	-0.553	-0.411	-0.331	-0.301
Ragi (variety I)	-0.501	-0.421	-0.322	-0.144
Ragi (variety II)	-0.502	-0.455	-0.333	-0.145
Wheat (white)	-0.555	-0.400	-0.301	-0.203
Wheat (brown)	-0.401	-0.302	-0.282	-0.017
Wheat (long and brown)	-0.411	-0.314	-0.273	-0.019
Sooji (variety I)			-0.332	-0.303
Sooji (variety II)			-0.288	-0.201
Wheat flour (maida)				-0.200
Paddy-IR 20 (raw)	-0.450	-0.302	-0.021	+0.118
Paddy-IR 8 (raw)	-0.412	-0.293	-0.011	+0.092
Paddy-IR 20 (boiled)	-0.443	-0.311	-0.022	+0.003
Paddy-IR (boiled)	-0.400	-0.288	-0.009	+0.001
Rice-IR 20 (raw)	-0.522	-0.500	-0.381	-0.300
Rice-IR 8 (raw)	-0.500	-0.482	-0.362	-0.288
Rice-IR 20 (boiled)	-0.511	-0.500	-0.377	-0.301
Rice-IR 8 (boiled)	-0.489	-0.480	-0.355	-0.288
Rice husk-IR 20 (raw)			+4.801	+5.023
Rice husk-IR 8 (raw)			+5.381	+5.222
Rice husk-IR 20 (boiled)			+5.001	+5.023
Rice husk-IR 8 (boiled)			+6.002	+6.031
Fenugreek	-0.441	-0.321	+0.111	+0.166
Cumin seeds	+0.620	+0.630	+0.700	+0.780
Ajowan	-0.072	-0.042	-0.301	-0.221
Black pepper	-0.322	-0.221	-0.165	-0.118
Coriander	-0.231	-0.200	-0.071	-0.062
Turmeric	-0.582	-0.022	+1.108	+1.592
Chilli fruits (dried)	-0.432	-0.401	-0.388	-0.362
Chille seed (dried)	-0.401	-0.362	-0.338	-0.278

The magnetic behavior of black gram on crushing was similar to that of green gram (Table 1). The peak of ESR signal of black gram lay centred at $g = 2.382$ which may be

compared with that of 2.34 ± 0.005 of nickel silicon fluoride complex at 29° . The results with the red gram are similar to those of black gram and green gram (Table 1). The ESR peak of red gram is at $g = 4.2001$ which can be compared with that of $4.15 + 0.015$ for Fe in MgO with the ratio Mg : Fe = 10^{-3} reported by Orton⁴ or with $g = 3.8 \pm 0.04$ in $\text{Fe}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_4\text{N}_2)_4$ reported by Ingram⁵.

Bengal gram husk is not tightly attached to the embryo unlike the husks of black gram, green gram and red gram; whereas other pulses of this family showed only a decrease in diamagnetic susceptibility upon crushing, Bengal gram with husk turned paramagnetic when ground to a fine powder (Table 1). Horse gram, cow pea, peas, millet, ragi, wheat, rice, paddy all behaved magnetically more or less in a similar manner when crushed (Table 1).

Wheat bran showed distinct paramagnetic behavior. The finer the bran the greater was the paramagnetic susceptibility. The peak of ESR signal of wheat husk was centred at $g = 2.01$. This may be compared with that of copper complex or copper ions⁶: $g = 2.07, 2.06, 2.116$ of Cu^{2+} in NaCl; $g = 2.12 \pm 0.02$ of $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)$. The free copper ions seem to produce ESR signal in the wheat husk. The ESR signals do not compare at all with iron complexes or ions as iron is a major possible contamination in these samples. Though majority of samples were hand-ground, even mill-ground samples did not have any iron impurity.

Both the raw and boiled rice showed diamagnetic susceptibilities (Table 1). When powdered, the flours showed a small decrease in diamagnetic susceptibility. However, the husk showed g value of 2.005. This may well be compared with that of potassium aluminium oxide complex or manganese complex as in the case of green gram³. Table 1 contains the results collected with fenugreek, cumin seeds, ajowan, black pepper, coriander seeds, turmeric and chillies. The results support our earlier findings. The oil cakes showed a net paramagnetism¹. The ESR spectrum of the samples confirms the result. The ESR signal of gingelly oil cake has a peak at $g = 2.271$ which may be compared with the g value Ni^{2+} ion in CaCl_2 and NiCl_2 powder ($g = 2.27$ at 50°)⁷.

The particular advantages of paramagnetic resonance in biological study are its ability to detect and characterize unpaired electrons and analyze the part that they play in the particular reactions under investigation. In this connection, one can divide biological studies into two main groups, viz. (a) those involving free-radicals in which the unpaired electron is moving in a large delocalized molecular orbital, and (b) those involving transition metal ions/atoms in which the unpaired electron is mainly localized on the par-

ticular atom itself. The presence and properties of various transition metal atoms can also play a very important part in various biochemical processes. Each of the biological compounds used in the present study contains a transition metal atom as an essential part of its constitution.

The ESR method is used to obtain information concerning the electronic charges, which might occur during the process of crushing. Zimmar *et al.*⁸ studied the production of free radicals in living cells. In their experiment they used embryos cut from resting barley seeds and subsequently X-rayed. They were able to record an ESR signal at $g = 2.00$ exhibiting a line width of 11 gauss. Conger and Randolph⁹ investigated the production of free radicals in cereal embryos by ionizing radiation. Barley seeds, barley embryos and wheat embryos were X-rayed and γ -rayed¹⁰. Doses of about 10 k rad were shown to produce detectable amounts of free radicals, but generally, large doses were used to produce higher concentration of unpaired spins. The production and decay of the signals were influenced by environmental conditions of irradiation and storage.

The reported ESR investigation of plant systems¹¹ corroborates the results of the present study : (a) ionizing radiations produce free radicals in plant materials, (b) the concentration of these radicals increases with increasing doses of radiation, and (c) the decay of free radicals concentration is slow, and therefore easily measurable for a long period after cessation of irradiation. Each of the ESR signals produced in the present study showed remarkable stability even after one month of crushing and at different storage conditions. However, as in the case of irradiation, the strength of the signal had an initial negligible decay and continued to a level where it became noticeable. The concentration of free radicals formed by powdering increases with increasing fineness of the sample.

After the paramagnetic induction in a sample by means of crushing, it was then subjected to ionizing radiation like ultraviolet, X-rays and γ -rays. Even after prolonged exposure to UV-light, the sample, for example, fenugreek powder did not show any increase in paramagnetic susceptibility nor did the ESR signal showed any change in size. Even exposure to X-rays and γ -rays did not produce any change in the magnetic susceptibility of ESR signal size. When the oils were γ -rayed for a period of over 10 h, there was no change in their magnetic properties. The oils were magnetically extremely radiation-resistant.

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